

Experiment: "Elicitation of context-aware functionalities"

Requirements validation checklist

Instructions:

- For each requirement, check the four criteria below one after another.
- If a requirement pass a certain criteria, you must evaluate the next criteria; if the requirement does not pass a certain criteria, you do not have to evaluate the next criteria.
- Requirements that pass the four criteria are considered VALID.

Criteria 1: AGREED

As defined in [1]: "A requirement is agreed upon if it is correct and necessary in the opinion of all stakeholders"

In the context of the experiment, the agreement is that the requirements must improve the user task in focus ("create a comment") with context awareness. That means that the requirements should be directly related to the user task and should describe a context-aware functionality (typically a recommendation or an adaptation – comprehensive description is available in [2]).

Criteria 2: FEASIBLE

As defined in [3]: "The requirement can be realized within system constraints (e.g., cost, schedule, technical) with acceptable risk."

In the context of the experiment, participants where informed that they were constrained to use only the contextual elements that they were told to use. Therefore if a requirement includes one contextual element that is not available, it should be considered unfeasible.

Criteria 3: NECESSARY

As defined in [3]: "(...) The requirement is currently applicable and has not been made obsolete by the passage of time. (...)"

In the context of the experiment, it means that the requirements should be coherent with the application and its existing capabilities. In case of doubts, an expert in the app (e.g. the product owner, or a representative user) should be consulted.

Criteria 4: COMPLETE

As defined in [3]: "The requirement sufficiently describes the necessary capability, characteristic, constraint or quality factor to meet the entity need without needing other information to understand the requirement."

[1] Pohl, K., Rupp, C.: Requirements engineering: fundamentals, principles, and techniques (2nd Edition). Rocky Nook (2015). [2] Dey, A.K.: Understanding and using context. PUC 5(1), 4–7 (2001). [3] ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148 - Systems and Software Engineering - Life cycle processes – Requirements engineering. Standard, ISO (2018).